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Factors Affecting Learning Loss due to COVID-19 for Students with Disabilities in India: A Secondary Data Analysis

Name of the Author:

Navjit Gaurav

Ph.D. Scholar at the School of Rehabilitation Therapy,
Queen's University, Kingston, Canada

navjit143.spa@gmail.com

Abstract

The education sector has suffered a significant hit due to COVID-19. UNESCO estimates about 65% drop out in school-going children, and among them, students with disabilities (from now on referred to as SWDs) are disproportionately represented. Globally, SWDs are at higher risk of dropping out of school, college and being unable to complete their education. The situation is similar in India, where SWDs cannot cope with online learning and risk dropping out of school. The learning loss due to COVID-19 for SWDs is less explored and needs immediate attention. This study explores the factors affecting learning loss due to COVID-19 for SWDs in India. Secondary data analysis employed analysis of various government reports and articles. Unprepared teacher/student, home-schooling, social isolation, school closure, and reduced employment opportunities significantly affected learning loss for SWDs. The study findings can inform the educational institutions and practitioners about the relevance of providing equal access

and strengthening the online learning platforms for SWDs. The study findings can enable policymakers and educational administrators to make informed decisions and plan actionable strategies to ensure continued access to learning opportunities for SWDs.

Keywords (6-8): Students with disabilities, learning loss, COVID-19, access, learning opportunities, e-learning, India.

Introduction

Education is crucial for an individual's overall growth and development as it empowers them to make an informed decision and have access to independent living opportunities. Education imparts learning that engenders awareness about resources and societal acceptance and can make an individual a productive member of their society. Additionally, education impacts health, psycho-social well-being, livelihood opportunities, and open avenues for an individual to learn and grow. Education for all is a global concern (UNICEF, 2013), and efforts are made to ensure globally no one is left behind (UNDP, 2019). Inaccessibility and limited or no access to education is a human rights issue (UNDP, 2019). The United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) aims to provide- "inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all by 2030" (Desa, 2016, p. 21). However, achieving this goal seems challenging as with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, all the sectors concerning education and development have experienced a cascading effect.

Global impact on education

Globally, the education sector has been affected severely by the COVID-19 pandemic, as 1.53 billion learners are out of school in 184 countries due to preventive measures like school closure

(UNESCO, 2021). A nationwide closure in 153 countries monitored by UNICEF and local closure in 24 countries would affect 98.6 percent of students worldwide. UNESCO estimates about 65 percent drop out in school-going children, and SWDs are disproportionately represented (UNESCO, 2020b). Globally, SWDs are at higher risk of dropping out of school, college and being unable to complete their education (UNESCO, 2020b).

Impact in India

The situation is similar in India, where 320 million students have been affected by school closure (UNESCO, 2020a), and only 37.6 million children across 16 states continue education through various education initiatives such as online classrooms and radio programs (UNICEF, 2020a). The SWDs are unable to cope with online learning (Krishna & Rajaraman, 2020), struggles and attend classes irregularly (Swabhimani, 2020), are at risk of dropping out of school, and are unable to complete their education. Unable to complete education puts SWDs and girls in the most vulnerable groups at risk of having compromised future opportunities. According to Ranjan (2020), about 77% of SWDs who cannot access distance learning methods felt they would fall behind in learning. Additionally, SWDs who lack access to the technologies and are forced to attend home-based learning have limited means to continue their education (PTI, 2021). Consequently, many SWDs may face the risk of never returning to school, undoing years of progress made in education leading to limited or no access to future opportunities for employment and growth.

Literature Review

Factors affecting education during COVID-19

COVID-19 had a multi-faceted influence on students' access to educational opportunities, particularly SWDs in low-resource environments. For instance, in India, where most of the population either live in the rural part of the country or low resource environments (informal settlements¹) of urban space. Researchers highlight multiple factors affecting the education of SWDs during the COVID-19 across various literature. Some of them include unprepared teachers/students for online education (Jena, 2020); home-schooling with increased parents' responsibility to teach their wards (Krishna & Rajaraman, 2020; Jena, 2020). The majority of the literature highlights that particularly underprivileged students cannot explore online learning opportunities due to limited access to the technologies and digital world (Jena, 2020; Menon & Unni, 2020).

The paradigm shift to online learning methods may exuberate the rural-urban divide (Kundu, 2020; Jena, 2020). There have been significant challenges in adaptation to new-age modern education approaches in rural India and urban low-resource environments (Kundu, 2020; Chowdhuri & Rohtagi, 2021). For instance, daily waged workers and often uneducated parents find it challenging to look after their children's home-schooling (Menon & Unni, 2020). This lack of parental guidance demotivates the child to continue their learning further due to no support at home. All the factors mentioned above collectively limit the learning opportunity and curb the SWDs for such subjective experiences.

1 Informal settlements are those settlements which are in urban spaces with limited basic facilities.

What is learning loss?

Researchers have used the term ‘educational loss’ and ‘learning loss’ interchangeably; however, there is a stark difference between these two terms. As suggested by (Surabhi 2021; Exley, 2021), education is a process of receiving and providing knowledge through systematic instruction, for example- school education. In comparison, learning is a life-long process (Exley, 2021). It involves an intellectual process of acquiring new skills and knowledge, through experience, social involvement, study, or teaching (Surabhi, 2021), for example- value-based learning. Learning involves students’ personal and environmental (physiological, psychological, and social) interaction (Kiswanto, 2017; Jarvela et al., 2019; Surabhi, 2021) to create opportunities to regulate their future actions and develop new knowledge (Surabhi, 2021). It is an organic or natural process (Surabhi, 2021; Jarvela et al., 2019) driven by the intrinsic motivation (Achiam & Sastry, 2017) of the students and can take place through day-to-day activities (Schlesinger et al., 2020), community life (Chambers, 2019), and interactions (Probine, 2021).

Most studies focus on educational loss and fail to cater to the need to explore learning loss which is crucial and embedded in the social environment and learning experience of the SWDs. Understanding the learning loss could provide insights into the psycho-social challenges SWDs are facing on a day-to-day basis staying inside their home in isolation. The factors affecting learning loss due to COVID-19 for SWDs are sporadically explored across studies and need immediate attention to bridge the learning gap and facilitate an advanced learning environment for them. Hence the core focus of this study is to explore the learning loss.

Problem statement

Access to education is a human right issue (McCowen, 2013); it empowers individuals to undertake informed decisions (Rieckman, 2018), has agency over choices/voice (Donnini, 2015), and independent living (Borntrager, 2006). Multiple factors can influence access to education (UNICEF, 2020). For instance, with the dearth of infrastructural facilities (Fagbohunka, 2017), limited trained teaching staff (Bajaj, 2011), inaccessible curriculum, and pedagogy (Menon & Unni, 2020) to access online education, it is anticipated that these factors will affect the learning and outcomes of many children in low-resource settings (UNICEF, 2020) like India. The SWDs are anticipated to be the worst affected by this online shift as they face challenges in understanding the instructions digitally due to limited acquaintance with this mode of learning (Krishna & Rajaraman, 2020). Learning loss is much more than just access to education as it influences the physio-psycho-social development of SWDs (Kumar, 2018) and is associated with their subjective experiences (Morgan et al., 2019; Spinelli, Lionetti, Pastore, & Fasolo, 2020). They understood the factors affecting learning loss due to COVID-19 and the relevance of an actionable approach to mitigate these so that SWDs could have a better future. Hence this secondary data analysis proposes to explore the factors affecting learning loss due to COVID-19 for SWDs in India.

Research Questions

- 1 What are the factors that affect learning loss for SWDs in India due to COVID-19?
- 1 How do these factors influence SWDs' learning loss?

Research Methodology

Method

This study employed a secondary data analysis method primarily been used in educational and evaluation research (McArt & McDoughal, 1985). This process allowed the researcher to examine the data more closely for latent content that reflects the detailed meaning of the responses (Rew et al., 2000) related to the study's objective. This approach was selected, as secondary data analysis is an efficient and cost-effective research method (McArt & McDoughal, 1985) for novice researchers and students (Smith, 2008). The method provided a time-saving opportunity to understand factors affecting learning loss due to COVID using the same empirical data with a different perspective (Koziol & Arthur, 2011).

Search Strategy

I performed an in-depth literature search for secondary data using the keywords- education loss, COVID-19, students with disabilities, learning opportunities, challenges, e-learning, access, strategies by government, India. I also included some phrases after the initial search, to explore further, these phrases included- 'education during COVID-19', 'education in India during COVID-19', 'education for students with disabilities amidst COVID-19', 'impact of COVID-19 on education', and 'Online learning during COVID in India.' I looked for the literature in the following databases: Google, Google Scholar, SCOPUS, Indian government websites like- Ministry of Education, Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, NGO websites for reports.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria for articles

The secondary data included the research papers published over the last ten years (focusing on the last two years) and

government and non-government reports of the past 4-5 years. Secondary data also included steps undertaken by various local and government bodies to mitigate the challenges associated with online learning. The analysis of several mitigation strategies employed by the authorities helped understand how the steps taken either bridge the gap or lead to a further digital divide for SWDs and their families. All the articles and reports dates before 2010 were excluded from the study. The articles not based on Indian contexts were also excluded. The author did a title and abstract screening for 20 documents (16articles + 4 reports) which were initially selected and excluded 12 as they did not relate to the education loss; the last eight documents (6 articles + 2 reports) were screened full text by the author and three documents were further excluded as they did not meet the study objective and were not related to the research question. Finally, the author ended up at the five related and suitable articles to answer the research question. Table 1 shows some of the critical articles and reports that somehow highlight the learning loss. All this existing empirical evidence highlights the potential shift in the Indian education system and how the learning loss has further intensified due to COVID-19.

Data Analysis

The analysis followed content analysis, and the researcher looked for contents across literature and government reports exploring the factors that affect learning loss and its impact on the physical and mental health, social life, and self-identity of SWDs. The initial analysis provided qualitative and quantitative results about the association among crucial factors and concepts affecting SWDs' learning loss due to online education patterns amidst COVID-19.

Later these findings were summarized and substantiated with the evidence-based findings from similar studies. A secondary analysis of the qualitative responses led to a more in-depth description (Johnston, 2017) of how the various factors coupled together can create further barriers related to the physio-psycho-social development of the SWDs.

Findings

Based on the literature reviewed, the researcher identified that there had been significant learning loss, and there are factors that affect the learning loss. The researcher proposes that “educational loss” should be considered as an objective approach to gauge unidirectional influences of socio-physical structure (people and institutions) on SWDs, whereas “learning loss” is the subjective experience of SWDs that accounts for the missed opportunities of experiential learning from the person-environment interaction, including places, peer-to-peer learning, activities, people, and objects. The predominance of learning loss for SWDs is anticipated to be higher than non-disabled students (Krishna & Rajaraman. Multiple factors might lead to significant learning loss (Jena, 2020), and these can be mitigated through an actionable approach to ensure inclusive access to learning for SWDs (refer to table 1. column four: bridge the gap strategies).

The factors highlighted initially that affect the educational loss, on a broader aspect, likely leads to significant learning loss to SWDs in India. The learning loss is associated with SWDs’ subjective experience while performing a task, participating in societal events in and out of home, and social interactions. The SWDs develop meaning for each of these experiences and imbibe the learning for their emotional and cognitive growth. For instance, the meaning could be an agency to participate, develop

Table 1

Factors affecting learning loss of Students with Disabilities during the COVID-19 period and E-Learning Resources

Title and Author	Factors affecting the learning of students with disabilities	Secondary data analysis & findings	E-Learning Resources during COVID-19	Bridge the gap strategies
Impact of pandemic covid-19 on education in India. (Jena, 2020)	Unprepared teachers/ students for online education.	We have reduced global employment opportunities.	Secondary education: Diksha portal, e-Pathshala, National Repository of Open Educational Resources (NROER) STEM-based games.	Accessible features in Diksha Portal, e-Pathshala, NROER with Sign Language accessibility, Colour Contrast, and Deaf-Blind Student accessibility features to be added. Low vision features to be added.
	Increased responsibility of parents to educate their wards.	Some may lose their jobs in other countries.		
	Access to the digital world.	Passing out students may not get their job outside India due to restrictions.	Higher Education Swayam Swayam Prabha e-PG Pathshala	Accessibility Features for all 21 types of disability-specific and common features to be added in All Higher Education portals like Swyam portal, E-PG Pathshala,
	Underprivileged students are unable to explore online learning.	Loss of nutrition due to school closure and impact on health.		

<p>The Paradigm Shift in the Indian Education System during COVID19: Impact, Opportunities, and Trends (Menon & Unni, 2020)</p>	<p>Parents (daily wagers) face difficulty managing children’s studies at home. Digital divide, with embedded gender and class divides.</p>	<p>There is a high peak in violence and exploitation. Anticipated trends in the post-COVID world. Fewer children will go back to school when schools reopen or will go out of town to study.</p>	<p>e-PG Pathshala CEC-UGC YouTube channel National Digital Library (NDL) National Academic Depository (NAD)</p>	<p>UGC guidelines with the inclusion of accessibility features on all universities’ websites all university websites shall comply with the W-3 guidelines of global accessibility standards. Accessible features with Sign Language accessibility, Colour Contrast, and Deaf-Blind Student accessibility features to be added. Low vision features to be added. Deploying E-learning methods can also assist special educators in reaching many children simultaneously. All of</p>
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<p>Impact of COVID-19 on School Education in India:</p>	<p>Engagement in economic activities and participation in household chores.</p>	<p>Social distancing, little or no sports.</p>	<p>National Knowledge Network (NKN)</p>	<p>this is possible only when the government takes an active interest in building technologies and capacities to make education truly inclusive and universal.</p>
<p>What is the Budgetary? Implications? (Kundu, 2020)</p>	<p>The quality of The electricity supply is impoverished, especially in rural India.</p>	<p>Globally, 23.8 million children (pre-primary to tertiary) - at risk of not returning to care centers, schools, and universities.</p>	<p>PM e-Vidya. The state takes initiatives Governments: i. Andhra Pradesh: Abhyasa ii. Kerala: Digitalisation of all school textbooks iii. West Bengal: TV Channels, WhatsApp,</p>	<p>Accessible features with Sign Language accessibility, Colour Contrast, and Deaf-Blind Student accessibility features to be added. Low vision features to be added.</p>
	<p>While 24 percent of Indians own a smartphone.</p>	<p>Out of these, 5.95 million are from South and West Asia (UNESCO, 2020b).</p>		<p>The term ‘inclusive education’ needs to be defined under the RTE Act. The Act should be amended and brought</p>

Impact of COVID -19 on Inclusive Education in India	Only 24 percent of Indian households have an internet facility.	A recent survey in West Bengal- child labor among school-going children has increased by 105 percent during the pandemic. Only 37.6 million children across 16 states are continuing education through online classrooms and radio.	and phone calls for doubt clearing sessions iv. Rajasthan: SMILE (Social Media Interface for Learning Engagement) v. Haryana: Ghar Se Padhao Abhiyan vi. Bihar: Unnayan– ‘Mera Mobile Mera Vidyalaya’	in line with the RPWD Act to update norms and standards to become inclusive, and guidelines should be issued under it for student and parent preparedness.
	Inaccessibility to Information and Communication Technologies.	Change in daily routines, lack of socialization, lack of emotional support, and change in means of learning have impacted the emotional state of children with disabilities.	National Council for Educational Research and Training (NCERT), inclusive online education.	Video content: Indian sign language and captioning, audio description of the video content not conveyed in the dialogue.

An Exploratory Research Proposal

(Krishna & Rajaraman, 2020)

Ineffectiveness of television-based lessons.

High dependence on parents.

Challenges in-home visitations by a teacher.

Challenges faced by teachers in acclimatizing to the online mode of education.

NGO involvement to provide individualized support.

Inaccessibility of disability-related benefits, nutritional supplements, and rehabilitation put the CWD at a higher risk than neurotypical children.

National Council for Educational Research and Training (NCERT), student's learning enhancement guidelines 2020-21

The Ministry of Social Justice
Furthermore, Welfare issued guidelines for the protection and safety of PWDs.

Provision of Compensatory Education.

Audiobooks: Indian sign language and captioning, effective navigation and browsing as per DAISY standards, caption to read along.

Image/picture or visual explanation of concepts: Textual description of the image, non-cluttered images, color contrast, and low vision features to be added.

Multi-sensory+ Indian sign language+ closed captioning +audio to be considered

The New Normal of the Education

System: Issues of Rights and Sustainability in Pandemic Trapped

India.

(Chowdhuri & Rohatgi, 2021)

UNESCO (2020c) data, 100 countries have not yet announced a date for schools to reopen; 65 have plans for partial or complete reopening.

Digital access- rural internet density is 25.3, while the urban internet density is 97.9.

The study materials are not available in vernacular languages. Children are not allowed smartphones.

School closure raises a range of ethical and social issues.

Underprivileged families- disproportionately affected.

Transitioning to online learning is a challenging and highly complex undertaking.

Adverse impact on learning outcomes and the social and behavioral development of children and young people.

Digital reach of education- categorized into three groups:

- online
- partially online
- offline mode

Digital access- rural internet density is 25.3, while the urban internet density is 97.9.

75% of SWDs never attend school.

Learning Enhancement Programmes and Models need to take into cognizance following challenges and concerns of learning during the COVID-19 period:

- For students not in school for a longer duration, there would be a visible gap in the learning level of students.
- Students have parents at risk due to their jobs.
- Children of migrant workers.

In the pandemic period, with an uncertain future facing all while planning any model for learning enhancement, the social-emotional aspects of learning need to be kept in view.

The use of mobile phones, television, and the internet in India is mainly for leisure and entertainment.

Children with internet problems walk 10 kilometers in the village in-network access zone and develop leg pain, acute fatigue, and discontinuing education due to regular school attendance.

The digital divide will widen existing gaps in inequality concerning education.

The citizens in the 'offline' category will suffer the most in the changing and challenging times.

This 'faceless' classroom-exhaust the participants.

Of the 6,572,999 children in the 5-19 age group, only 61.18 percent (4,021,301) have attended any educational institution. This was well below the national average of 70.97 percent for children in all categories.

Some 26.68 percent (1,753,737) have never attended any educational institute compared to the national average of 17.21 percent. About 12.14 percent (797,961) attended one but dropped out later.

Accessibility of devices, ICTs, resources, building infrastructure, Affordability of the devices and resources to the larger population in remote and rural areas.

Capacity building of teachers and caregivers.

Promoting home-based schooling as an acceptable feature under RTE.

Mapping the curriculum, reducing contents, and creating refreshers programs for the learning loss of students with disabilities.

social bonds, interact with friends and peers, and contribute to society's development. The subsequent paragraphs talk about the factors affecting learning loss from a psycho-social lens.

Learning loss due to unprepared teachers/students

Online learning leads to compromised learning experiences for the SWDs as they have poor access to resources, ICTs, internet, and even if they have access to these resources, the online interface is not disabled-friendly. This is further aggravated as the teachers have limited accessible tools for online instructions (Krishna & Rajaraman, 2020), and most of them are not adequately trained (Jena, 2020) to conduct need-based online learning sessions for SWDs. As SWDs could not comprehend the online instructions comprehensively, they failed to accept this online mode (Jena, 2020). When they are dependent on someone (people as environment) for their learning, they find it challenging to navigate and get frustrated. The imitation of E-learning is its unfriendly user interface (Kundu, 2020), making it difficult for the SWDs to comprehend the learning materials, maintain their attention, retain what they see on online platforms, and simultaneously assimilate the learnings (Ranjan, 2020). The SWDs develop fatigue, stress, anxiety, and it hampers their cycle of learning- attention, sensory process, analysis, memory, retention, assimilation, etc., which was possible in the offline mode of learning with the continued support of peers, teacher, and caregivers.

Learning loss with home-schooling

Due to the shift to online learning, SWDs and their parents either do not have access to advanced technology (Jena, 2020) or, if they do, they are not accustomed to using these efficiently. They lack the understanding of even operating technological

devices and have difficulty using these applications. As a result, the parental involvement, guidance, and support that could lead to the reinforcement of a positive approach toward learning are missed (Menon & Unni, 2020), affecting SWDs' psycho-social growth. Also, the SWDs with limited digital literacy, understanding regarding the use of the internet, devices, understanding of online platforms, social media, other media platforms to learn, participate, and contribute miss the opportunity and have a negative experience from online learning and due to that they refrain attending the class regularly (Kundu, 2020). In most cases, parents cannot afford such devices (Krishna & Rajaraman, 2020), and with no device to access online learning (Chaudari & Rohatgi, 2021), SWDs are left behind to drop out of class then continue for nothing.

This process of unfamiliar home-schooling and learning loss is diverting children into loneliness (Chowdhuri & Rohatgi, 2021), lack of social play (Menon & Unni, 2020), a sense of low self-esteem (Krishna & Rajaraman, 2020), and they are unable to follow the learning routine of online learning (Chowdhuri & Rohatgi, 2021). Also, Children with poor network and access to the internet walk 10 kilometers in the village on network access zone and develop leg pain, acute fatigue, and discontinue education as they cannot maintain regularity in school. These adverse experiences are internalized so much that SWDs can take years of effort to overcome with continued irregularity. These adverse experiences are internalized so much that SWDs can take years of effort to overcome with continued irregularity.

Learning loss due to school closure

Studies highlight that the change in daily routines, engaging in home chores, lack of socialization, lack of emotional support, and change in means of learning had affected the emotional

state of SWDs (Kundu, 2020). In addition, with school closure, the in-person connection is missing. SWDs miss opportunities to retain and make social connections engage in personal conversation with their friends and peers. During this time, SWDs' social environment includes people, places, and objects that do not facilitate conducive learning opportunities to inculcate their emotional and cognitive development. School closure impacts mental and physical health as well, as there is a lack of outdoor physical activities that make them prone to various health disorders (Chowdhuri & Rohatgi, 2021).

Learning loss due to social isolation

Missing the in-person connection due to lockdown leads to inadequate learning opportunities and social isolation. Social isolation refers to staying inside the home with no social support and fear of getting affected by COVID-19 if they socialize. Although, with the prevailing societal stigma around disability, SWDs have been living in isolation for so long (Agrawal, 2020). However, the COVID-19 pandemic was triggered further, and those who could have recovered from this isolation in everyday life are further pushed back. All the efforts to promote the learning experience with an inclusive education philosophy (Lindsey, 2007), where inclusion means that children are physically present and socially included (Bhan & Rodricks, 2013), are gone in vain.

Social isolation is likely to lead to aggressive behavioral change in SWDs. Frustration, anxiety, anger, and irritation become habitual behavior for them (Rajan, 2020). The entire experience of being in a homely environment, staying close to family, and support, go in vain, and the SWDs are at higher risk of experiencing traumatic episodes and could hurt themselves in isolation.

Learning loss due to reduced employment opportunities

With the onset of COVID-19 induced lockdown, significant job losses and reduced employment opportunities (Deshpande & Ramachandran, 2020). A report by United Nations Human Rights (2020) highlights that individuals with disabilities who are employed or self-employed (United Nations, 2019) “ maybe prevented from working from home due to the absence of equipment and support which are available in the workplace and face increased risks of losing their income and job” (p. 5). The qualified SWDs may not get their job within India due to restrictions caused by COVID-19 (Jena, 2020) and unprecedented recessions in the employment sector (Raman et al., 2021). Data from the survey by the National Centre for Promotion of Employment for Disabled People of 1067 individuals with disabilities (approx. 73% male and 27% female) shows that about 57% of individuals with disabilities, including students, are facing a financial crisis and job loss (NCPEDP, 2020, p.13). The situations are even worse when it comes to female SWDs (NCPEDP, 2020). The opportunity that the SWDs might have for life-long learning (Jena, 2020) and experience that could help them develop the skill required for working in the industry, social capital (Rai, 2020), psychological and emotional contentment (Seevers & Lopez, 2021) through on-the-job placement (Garg, 2017) is curbed due to COVID-19.

Discussion

This study is unique in its approach as it explores the learning loss concerning the subjective experience of SWDs (Carvalho et al., 2020), which they obtain while interacting with their physio-psycho-social environment (Jena, 2020). Moreover, looking at the subjective experience from a psycho-social lens could enable

us to explore the extent of emotional and cognitive growth of SWDs that the COVID-19 pandemic has impacted (Chowdhuri & Rohatgi, 2010). The study is noble as it emphasizes experiential learning of SWDs, rather than traditional learning, and contributes to building discussion around the experiential learning loss that leads to negative consequences on their mental and physical health (Krishna & Rajaraman, 2020). These analytical findings also resonate with India's National Education Policy (NEP, 2020) philosophy that attempts to transition from the traditional education model to more experiential learning approaches by including vocational training, skill development, and instruction in the local language to promote inclusion and diversity. National Education Policy intended to promote skill-based learning and develop scientific temper from a young age to improve the quality of higher educational institutes and bring them at par with the global standards (Panditrao & Panditrao, 2020). However, pandemic-induced lockdown and restrictions have compromised the ambitions of National Education Policy which looked promising and in the right direction. Moreover, COVID-19 has pushed us way behind even thinking about such experiential learning provisions when the population is fighting to survive and thrive (Menon & Unni, 2020).

This study highlighted the factors affecting learning loss due to the online mode of education and its effect on the emotional, social, physical, and cognitive growth of SWDs. These findings resonate with the World Bank (2021), recognizing that the transition to online learning at scale is challenging and highly complex for education systems.

Consequences of school closure

There is a high peak at violence and exploitation (Menon & Unni, 2020). Evidence-based literature highlights that

when schools are shut down, early marriages increase, sexual exploitation of girls and young women rises, teenage pregnancies become more common, and child labor grows (Kundu, 2020). Exploiting the SWDs with no support at home is so common. SWDs undergoing such violence and exploitation are at increased risk of mental or physical stress that could have a long-lasting impression (Chaudhari & Rohatgi, 2021). With the dearth of child counseling opportunities, the mental well-being of SWDs is at stake, further making them vulnerable to violence.

Government initiatives and way forward

The initiatives so far are not enough and inclusive to cater to disability-related needs of SWDs and could lead to inevitable and irreparable learning loss if not addressed with relevant, actionable measures. Several government initiatives have been to bridge the digital divide and promote better learning experiences to the learners (Diksha portal, e-PG pathshala, etc.) (refer to table 1). However, they knowingly or unknowingly missed the opportunity to facilitate comprehensive, inclusive, and accessible learning. Since the larger population is not digitally aware and informed to use these online portals, there is limited acceptability of these platforms by the caregivers and SWDs. In addition to that, the availability of resources to the SWDs is access, and if there is a certain amount of investment required, then the affordability of these resources further leads to loss of learning. So, considering the Indian population size and limitation of resources and infrastructure, collaborating with NGOs can help to extend the learning benefit of online mode transition during the pandemic to children. Through their community outreach, NGOs can provide individualized support to the SWDs and create a healthy home-schooling learning environment for both SWDs and families. The government could also provide the

families with activity kits and create awareness around using household materials as a medium of experiential learning and craft activities. The Play way method with hands-on experience with different materials is likely to inculcate a better learning experience and provide opportunities to SWDs that their friends might have (Kiswanto, 2017).

In addition, government and local organizations could collectively provide basic digital literacy to the caregivers and teachers and adapt the pedagogy using a universal design of learning (UDL). UDL allows for creating facilities that are not only accessible (objective) but also usable (subjective); usability is the effective, efficient, comfortable, convenient and engaging way (Iwarsson & Stahl, 2003) to provide a learning experience to the children. Moreover, the usability of the facilities is assessed using field experience (Imrie & Hall, 2003), and this is where the NGOs can play an active part. Also, usability has an activity component (Iwarsson & Stahl, 2003), making the provisions more experiential for the users (SWDs in this case), and they can learn a lot from these experiences.

Current pedagogy focuses mainly on educational gain. However, after the COVID-19 pandemic is over, we can build on the study findings related to the concept of learning loss and create an infrastructure that provides opportunities for comprehensive learning experiences. There has been a significant gap in online education highlighted in the paragraphs above, and there is a need for a future road map with equal accessibility measures and provision in E-Learning resources and online learning provision in school education in coherence with UNCRPD.

Conclusion

Each situation has its pros and cons and affects individuals differently. The present pandemic situation and its effect on

the education sector cannot be overlooked in India. We need to develop innovative strategies to ensure the learning and development of the learners are not affected further (refer to table 1). Adapting to a digital literacy strategy could be one such step. Also, the facilities and opportunities should be created on an equal basis for all irrespective of caste, class, gender, ability, language, rural/urban background. The strategies should adhere to three As strategies- Affordable, Accessible, and Acceptable. One such strategy would be to adopt a universal design strategy to maximize the use of the services and provide a better learning experience. Responsible authorities need to collaboratively work to deal with the poor access to education for all. Also, focusing on what resources we have and how we can adapt to them and broaden the access using those resources can be an effective strategy. These strategies are likely to create an enabling environment that can nurture meaningful participation and learning experience for SWDs. There are high chances that fewer SWDs will go back to school when the school reopens (Menon & Unni, 2020; Sholas, Apkon and Houtrow, 2021), considering the internalized incapability of the learning pedagogy to engage them in the experiential learning process (American Academy of Paediatrics, 2021). It is anticipated that the effect of COVID-19 induced lockdowns and social distancing might lead to many SWDs getting socially distant (Carvalho et al., 2020).

Scope of the study

The scope of this study focused on the learning loss of SWDs due to the COVID-19 pandemic and provided insights into the implication of these research findings. For instance, the study findings can inform the educational institutions and practitioners about the relevance of providing equal access and strengthening the online learning platforms for SWDs. Additionally, the study

findings can enable policymakers and educational administrators to make informed decisions and plan actionable strategies to ensure continued access to learning opportunities for SWDs. Considering the learning loss as an essential aspect of SWDs' psycho-social growth. Future research could consider exploring the learning loss and its immediate effect on the SWDs. Further research can also investigate the family-school partnerships or parent-teacher partnerships to provide insights for adapting an experiential learning pedagogy. Researchers could also explore the impact of SWDs' learning loss on the mental health of families and caregivers.

Study limitations

The study provides comprehensive insights into the importance of learning loss; however, this analysis has limitations. The analysis did not look thoroughly into the psychological literature, which is embedded in the subjective experience, social interactions, activities in and out of the home. Moreover, this study is limited as it does not provide detailed insights into the effect of learning loss for the post-COVID world.

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Declaration of conflict of interest

Since it is sole authorship, so there was no conflict of interest. Moreover, all the reports and articles cited are given due credits.

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